

Spectrophotometric determination of colchicine using iron(III) chloride and 1,10-phenanthroline

D. K. Singh*, Bhavana Srivastava and Archana Sahu

Analytical Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, H. B. Technological Institute, Kanpur-208 002, India

E-mail : dhruvks123@rediffmail.com

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A new spectrophotometric method for the quantitative determination of colchicine in pure and its pharmaceutical formulations has been developed. The method involves the oxidation of colchicine by iron(III) chloride and subsequent complexation of iron(II) with 1,10-phenanthroline forming a red coloured complex having maximum absorbance at 510 nm. Beer's law holds well in the concentration range 5–50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The common excipients do not interfere with the proposed method. The results of the proposed method are in good agreement with the reported method and show no significant difference in the precision.

Colchicine is derived from the naturally occurring alkaloid in *Colchicum autumnale*. It is used in the treatment of gouty arthritis, condyloma acuminata, Behcet's syndrome, cancer and chronic cutaneous leucocytoclastic vasculitis¹. Several methods such as HPLC^{2–6}, fluorometry^{7,8}, polarography⁹ and immunoassay¹⁰ have been reported for the determination of colchicine. Non-aqueous titration for colchicine in pure as well as in pharmaceutical formulations is described in British Pharmacopoeia¹¹. Although, spectrophotometric method is very common, but no report on the colorimetric method for the determination of colchicine has been registered.

The proposed spectrophotometric method is based on the oxidation of colchicine with iron(II) in acidic medium and subsequent complexation of iron(II) with 1,10-phenanthroline forming a red coloured complex (λ_{max} 510 nm). It is simple, accurate and readily applicable for the determination of colchicine in pharmaceutical formulations.

Results and discussion

Colchicine is oxidized by iron(III) chloride in the acidic medium and produces iron(II). The iron(II) reacts with 1,10-phenanthroline and produces orange red tris-1,10-phenanthrolineiron(II) ion (ferroin) having absorption maxima at 510 nm. The general reaction mechanism is given below :

Effect of variables : The reaction conditions were established by varying one parameter at a time and keeping others constant. Maximum and constant absorbance was found with $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration of FeCl_3 and $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration of 1,10-phenanthroline and were therefore adopted as optimal.

The colour reaction for colchicine occurred even at RT though at higher temperature colour developed more rapidly (Fig. 1). A temperature of $70 \pm 2^\circ$ and a reaction time of 30 min were selected for reproducible results.

Analytical features : The method obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range 5–50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ with molar absorpti-

Fig. 1. Effect of time and temperature on the absorbance of colchicine ($40 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$).

vity value of $4 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. A regression analysis of Beer's law plot revealed a good correlation ($r = 0.9998$). The absorbance versus concentration of colchicine plot showed a almost zero intercept (0.002002) and slope (0.009709); and is described by the regression equation, $Y = bX + a$, where Y is absorbance of 1 cm layer, b is the slope, a is the intercept and X is the concentration of colchicine in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ obtained by least square method. The low relative standard deviation values for the analysis of five replicates of the colchicine indicates a good precision and accuracy of the proposed method.

Interference studies: In order to assess the possible analytical applications of the proposed method, the effect of some substances that often accompany colchicine in various pharmaceutical formulations was studied by adding different amounts of the substances to $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of colchicine. The colour was developed following the procedure described earlier. A substance was considered to interfere with the determination if the obtained absorbance values differed by more than $\pm 2\%$ from that for the drug alone. It was observed that talc, glucose, starch, lactose, dextrose did not interfere with the determination at the levels found in the dosage forms. Thus, the proposed method is free from interferences by the investigated foreign substances.

Application of the method: The applicability of the proposed method has been examined for the determination of colchicine in the pharmaceutical formulations. The results of the assay of colchicine in the tablets were comparable with the quoted values and those obtained by official method¹¹.

Statistical analysis: The performance of the proposed method was judged by calculating student t -test and variance ratio F -test. At 95% confidence level the calculated t - and F -values do not exceed the theoretical values (Table 1), indicating that there was no significant difference between the precisions of the proposed and official methods.

Table 1. Analysis of colchicine in pharmaceutical preparations

Drug	Recovery ^a , %		t^b	F
	Proposed method	Official method		
Colchicine (Sigma, U.S.A)	100.61 \pm 0.97	100.12. \pm 0.80	0.870	1.470
Colchicindon (Indon, India)	99.0 \pm 1.0	99.6 \pm 0.90	0.996	1.234
Goutnil (Inga, India)	99.2 \pm 0.72	99.5 \pm 0.69	1.290	1.088

^aMean \pm S.D. for 5 determinations, based on label claim.

^bTheoretical value = 2.78 ($P = 0.05$).

Conclusion :

From an analytical point of view, it is concluded that the described procedure allows for the determination of colchicine in pure and pharmaceutical dosage forms. Unlike the spectrofluorometer as well as gas chromatographic and HPLC procedures, the instrument is simple and inexpensive. Its importance lies in the chemical reaction upon which the procedure is based, rather than upon the sophistication of the instrument. This aspect for spectrophotometric analysis is of major interest in analytical pharmacy, since it offers a distinct possibility in the assay of a particular component in dosage formulations.

Experimental

An Elico SL 164 spectrophotometer having matched 1 cm quartz cells was used. Colchicine (Sigma, U.S.A.) was used. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade.

Stock solution of colchicine was prepared by dissolving colchicine (100 mg) in ethanol (~10 ml) and diluted to 100 ml with double-distilled water. Working solutions were prepared by appropriate dilutions of stock solution. Solutions of $0.025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ iron(III) chloride in 0.5 mol dm^{-3} HCl and 0.05 mol dm^{-3} 1,10-phenanthroline in ethanol were prepared.

Procedure: Aliquots of standard solutions of colchicine were transferred in to a series of 10 ml calibrated flasks. To each of these flasks were added 1 ml of FeCl_3 and 1 ml of 1,10-phenanthroline solutions and diluted to mark with water. The flasks were heated in a water-bath ($70 \pm 2^\circ$) for 30 min. The absorbance of the red coloured products was measured against a reagent blank at 510 nm.

Procedure for pharmaceutical formulations: For assay of dosage forms, 20 tablets were mixed, crushed and carefully weighed. A quantity of powder equivalent to 10 mg of colchicine was weighed accurately dissolved as described above and filtered. The filtrate was made up to 100 ml with water and a suitable amount of aliquot was treated as described above for a pure colchicine.

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